

Navigating formalisation: Migrant hostel dwellers and the UK banking system

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Why look at Banks?

- ▶ **Not initial part of research.** Initial research focus on new government policies on modern slavery and labour exploitation.
- ▶ Attended policy events and conducted ethnographic fieldwork in a London Hostel over 18 months living and working with people who in labour exploitation policy contexts are often portrayed as being problematic.
- ▶ **Getting an bank account as major concern for migrants with implications on:**
 - ▶ Job opportunities
 - ▶ Housing options
 - ▶ Financial safeguards
 - ▶ Migration status
- ▶ **Good to explore formalisation/informalisation dynamics as a site that tie in with**
 - ▶ Global and national policy processes
 - ▶ Economic transformations and uncertainties
 - ▶ Technological changes
 - ▶ Everyday practices of state-economic encounters

Why was it difficult to get a bank account?

- ▶ **Customer due diligence.** The UK government requires banks have to carry out checks to insure the identity of their customers
- ▶ **UK anti-money laundering regime.** This is part of policies (informed by global norms) that seek to deal with '*money laundering as a critical enabler of serious and organised crime, grand corruption, and terrorism*' (HO Action Plan for anti-money laundering and counter-terrorist finance, 2016)
- ▶ **Complex sets of regulations, guidance, and interpretations.**
 - ▶ The Money Laundering, Terrorist Financing and Transfer of Funds Regulations 2017 (SI 2017 No. 692)
 - ▶ The Criminal Finances Act 2017
 - ▶ The Proceeds of Crime Act 2002 (as amended by the Crime and Courts Act 2013 and the Serious Crime Act 2015)
 - ▶ The Money Laundering Regulations 2007 (SI 2007 No. 2157)
 - ▶ The Terrorism Act 2000 (as amended by the Anti-Terrorism, Crime and Security Act 2001, the Terrorism Act 2006 and the Terrorism Act 2000 and Proceeds of Crime Act 2002 (Amendment) Regulations 2007).
- ▶ **Encourages a risk based approach:** Banks should focus '*Their efforts on the highest risks, without troubling low risk clients with unnecessary red-tape*' HO Action Plan for anti-money laundering and counter-terrorist finance, 2016).

Practical manifestations of customer due diligence policies

Overall company policies

Local branch policies

Bank clerks interpretations

Most high street banks requires:

► Proof of identity

Proof of UK address

Date	Description	Debit	Credit	Balance
20 Jun	Balance brought forward			6450.00
22 Jun	VIS	11.46		6438.54
23 Jun	VIS	2000.00		4438.54
01 Jul	DO	10.00		4428.54
01 Jul	SD	5.00		4423.54
03 Jul	CR		39.00	4462.54
05 Jul	ATM	100.00		4362.54
15 Jul	BP	780.00		3582.54
15 Jul	VIS	15.30		3567.24
15 Jul	CR			3567.24
17 Jul	SD	700.00		2867.24
16 Jul	ATM	100.00		2767.24
20 Jul	Balance carried forward			2767.24

Characteristics of the hostel, the people in it, and the 'documentation'

- **Hostel**

- Hostel 'normal' online bookable hostel
- No reception or permanent staff
- Little formal checks when moving in
- Only paid in cash

- **People**

- Hostel mix of tourist and workers
- Between 18-62 years old
- All kinds of nationalities and backgrounds.
- Stayed between 3 days and 5 years

- **Documents**

- First time bookings get a 'contract' thereafter no documentation provided including receipts.

Performing banking identities

- ▶ Providing formal proof of address impossible.
- ▶ Used a range of different strategies to overcome that:
- ▶ **Exchanging of knowledges:** Learning from fellow hostel dwellers where the 'good' bank branches where or which clerk to speak with.
- ▶ **Documents:** Work contracts, 'modified' hostel contracts, letters from hostel staff, other types of picture ids. Bank cards from other countries.
- ▶ **Embodied characteristics:** Presenting certain types of visualities seemed to be more successful than others: Ties in with **Class, race, ethnicity, disability, age**
- ▶ **Online apps/banks/credit options:** Possible to set up online bank accounts in other countries with less strict policies, but where it is possible to get a UK bank account number as well as documents with your address being written as being in the UK.

Consequences of the banking encounters

- Some people get a bank account within a day.
- For others it took several months.
- Some never got a bank account and had to continue to work in informal and low paid jobs.
- Some 'disappeared' after failing to get a bank account.

Theoretical questions

- ▶ **What is the state?** globally entangled and culturally linked state processes and perceptions in possession of complex social lives that are shaped by a number of different actors, institutions and other artefacts which, in combination, lead to often unexpected and unplanned results.
- ▶ **What is a policy?** An actant' that takes on certain material properties and is formed through spatial and historical contingencies in interplay with other social agents and everyday organisational, bureaucratic and social practices
- ▶ **How does processes of formalisation/informalisation work?** Although complex processes is involved in shaping the banking encounter, these formalising '**checkpoints**' requires binary decisions. Checkpoints are spaces that are created to slow down the flow of social-economic life so as to make these flows visible and orderable. It is also placed where 'the security of identity and rights can become suddenly and sometimes violently unsettled' (Das and Poole, 2004, p. 10)
- ▶ **Issues of agency:** Possible to navigate and circumvent checkpoints, but your chance of success depended on a range of different social factors that creates particular forms of exclusion and inclusion.